

Environmental performance evaluation using the frontier analysis framework

Technical brief

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Summary

The environmental spillover effect of economic activities has been the uppermost concern of policymakers and academicians over the last two decades across Europe and beyond. It is also a major aim of forthcoming agricultural legislation in Scotland, and related legislation on, for example, nitrates, sustainable use of pesticides or water quality. The Scottish government has committed to achieving net zero greenhouse gas (GHG) emissions by 2045 and agriculture as a sector must decarbonise through the uptake of sustainable 'win-win' measures. These are practices or technologies which both maintain or enhance production whilst also reducing carbon emissions. Hence, environmental performance, on its own and in relation to productivity, is an important foundation to inform policy and industry initiatives aimed at reducing environmental impact.

A proper evaluation of the environmental performance of farms and countries' production systems requires a tool that allows the integration of environmental concerns in the evaluation process (Tyteca, 1996). Environmental efficiency measurement using the frontier analysis framework is one of the environmental performance evaluation tools used in recent times. Yet, finding a universally agreed environmental efficiency measurement remains a challenge.

The main aim of this brief is to provide an overview of the frontier-based approaches to measure environmental efficiency as an environmental performance indicator. We also highlight the work in progress on the environmental performance evaluation of Scottish agriculture using the Farm Business Survey (FBS) data.

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Environmental performance evaluation based on frontier analysis

Frontier-based approaches to environmental efficiency (EE) analysis rest on the assumption that, at any point in time, there is an ideal level of environmental performance and efficient resource use that farms of a specific production type could achieve. This ideal level is called the frontier. Frontier-based approaches to understanding environmental performance quantify the relative distance of farms from the ideal performance level. It is also worth noting that the frontier can move over time, reflecting, for example, technological advances that enhance efficiency and environmental performance. Environmental performance evaluations using the frontier analysis framework can be classified into four methods.¹ Figure 1 summarizes these methods based on their advantages and potential limitations.

I. Environmentally adjusted production efficiency: in this method, the relationship between inputs and outputs is analysed by considering pollutants as environmentally detrimental inputs (e.g., Nitrogen fertilizer application) or undesirable outputs (e.g., CO₂ emissions). The EE of economic units is derived by estimating a production function that accounts for pollutants as additional variables in the form of input or output. It seeks the maximum increment in desired output while simultaneously reducing the level of undesired output. This means that for a given level of input, decision-making units are credited for their expansion of desirable output and simultaneous contraction of undesirable output. Despite it being a conventional and widely used method of environmental efficiency measurement, it has been criticized due to its violation of the first law of thermodynamics (Coelli et al., 2007; Hoang & Nguyen 2013). The first law of thermodynamics states that the total amount of mass in the inputs should be equal to the mass (material) in the desirable output plus the mass in the undesirable output (pollution).

II. Frontier Eco-efficiency: unlike the common inputs and outputs used in the production efficiency analysis, this method relates economic and environmental outcomes by operationalizing the traditional eco-efficiency concept in a stochastic frontier framework.² It evaluates the relative performance of economic units using a pollution-generating technology set (eco-efficient frontier), which describes all the feasible combinations of economic value and environmental damage. Hence, environmental eco-efficiency is said to be attained in this approach if and only if it is impossible to reduce environmental damage without simultaneously decreasing economic value.

This approach is cost-effective and easy for policymakers to implement as it does not put physical restrictions on the level of economic activity. Since it is difficult to restrict/ limit the level of economic activities, implementing policies that target improving eco-

¹ Earlier approaches to environmental performance measurement, like environmental impact assessment and the life cycle assessment approach do not allow comparison among different units and over time which limits their applicability relative to frontier-based approaches (see Tyteca, 1996).

² Broadly, eco-efficiency can be defined as 'the efficiency with which ecological resources are used to meet human needs' (OECD, 1998). It specifically indicates an economic unit's capacity to produce valuable economic goods and services with a minimal environmental impact.

efficiency is easier. However, it is a relative measure of sustainability and not an absolute indicator. It measures the share of environmental pressure relative to the volume of economic activity, while an absolute indicator is important for sustainability measurement.³ Eco-efficiency improvements at the micro level do not guarantee environmental sustainability at the macro level. For instance, an increase in food consumption worldwide could nullify the per-unit eco-efficiency gains. This is especially substantial if there is a shift in consumption towards products which bear a larger environmental impact. Examples of this are an increase in the consumption of meat, or an increase in travelling (Picazo-Tadeo et al., 2011).

Fig. 1: Environmental performance evaluation methods based on frontier analysis.

III. **The material balance approach:** the third approach is based on the Material Balance Principle (MBP), which states that in any closed production system “**what goes in must come out.**” In the context of EE, the MBP implies that materials which are not contained in a good output will be released to the environment as potential pollutants. Hence, this approach measures environmental performance by minimizing the level of residual pollutant nutrients released to the environment. Nevertheless, it has two main limitations. First, the MB method does not appropriately treat immaterial inputs. In this approach, the

³ Eco-efficiency improvements do not guarantee sustainability since the overall environmental impact of activity will surpass the carrying capacity of the ecosystem even though the relative level of environmental externality is low compared to economic output (Kuosmanen and Kortelainen, 2005). Due to various practical contexts that eco-efficiency improvements fail to account for, an absolute indicator of sustainability is important to appropriately measure the environmental impact of economic activities. For instance, producing fuel-efficient cars seems to be eco-efficient. However, this means that the same trip costs less now which encourages to drive and pollute more called a rebound effect.

material content of immaterial inputs, such as labour and capital, are considered zero even if a positive value of these inputs has been used. This implies that environmental efficiency measured employing this method only focuses on minimizing the nutrient content in the material inputs. It implies that it overestimates the environmental efficiency of economic units that use less material inputs irrespective of immaterial inputs. Second, there is not a universally accepted measurement for the weight of nutrient content of the material inputs. When more than one material input is involved in the production process, determining the aggregate pollution would be challenging. Using the polluting power of different inputs as weights for aggregation could be one way of accounting for this. For example, a proportion of 10:1 was used to account for the pollution of phosphorus and nitrogen assuming that the atrophying capacity of phosphorus is ten times higher than that of nitrogen (Coelli et al., 2007). However, material inputs may not pose a single environmental damage (e.g., eutrophication) and most often, production processes involve different material inputs like fuel, electricity, wood, and coal, which results in diverse environmental impacts (e.g., gas emissions). Hence, the MB approach does not allow the joint analysis of material and energy consumption.

IV. The exergy balance approach: drawing on the second law of thermodynamics, this approach argues that agricultural sustainability should focus on the analysis of the cumulative extraction of the total environmental resources that account for both the quantity and quality of these resources; that is, on the analysis of exergy. Thus, environmental performance is measured as the proportion of total exergy released into the environment as a potential pollutant relative to the minimum feasible amount of exergy for a given level of input use. Through this, it overcomes the two limitations of the MBP method.⁴ The advantage of the exergy balance approach lies in its capacity to use a common physical unit called the exergy unit to express all physical inputs, allowing a holistic analysis of resource use efficiency. Yet, estimating the exergy content of each input and output used in the production process remains a challenge to the wide applicability of this method. For instance, it is difficult to determine the exergy content of man-made capitals, such as buildings and services including research and development training inputs.⁵

Work in progress

Our research team is currently working on understanding environmental performance in Scottish agriculture and beyond. The first main work package related to this is a meta-analysis and systematic review of environmental efficiency studies conducted so far. This

⁴ Exergy can be defined as a measure of the quantity and quality of any matters, materials and energy forms contained in the stock and the flows of natural resources. Using the exergy, we can describe various types of resources in terms of a common physical unit, which is an expression of quantity and quality.

⁵ Empirical applications also excluded the exergy from solar radiation, winds and geothermal heat as these exergy sources were much larger than the exergy of other inputs and the analysis of other inputs would be less sensible if the analysis included exergy from these sources (see, Hoang and Rao 2010; Hoang and Alauddin, 2011).

enables us to broadly understand the previous literature on environmental efficiency and the potential limitations and challenges faced. Moreover, it allows us to identify the role of different environmental efficiency measurements, regional differences and structural factors, such as agricultural policies impact the level of environmental performance across different farming systems.

In the second work package, we evaluate the environmental performance of Scottish agriculture across different farming systems using the Farm Business Survey (FBS) data. The FBS collects detailed financial and production-related data for a set of farms in Scotland. The depth of the survey offers an understanding of the financial performance of farms over time. Since 2019/2020 farmers who had completed the FBS were also asked to carry out a carbon audit. This involved a further detailed interview with each farmer to complete the carbon calculator 'Agrecalc' (Sykes et al., 2017; Kamilaris et al., 2020). 'Agrecalc' is a farm-level tool for measuring resource efficiency to improve profitability and environmental impact. The tool uses Tier 2 calculations and employs information on detailed inputs as well as mixes of outputs at the farm level. The 'Agrecalc' farmer interview provided valuable data on the provenance of all imported and home-produced inputs and outputs, as well as the underlying biophysical and management aspects of the farm. Another advantage is that using the FBS as the basis to estimate farm-level emissions gives confidence that emission and financial data have been reported consistently for all farms.

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